

Web2Learn
Open. social learning

Forms of citizen engagement in cultural heritage preservation: examples from the war in Ukraine

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Europeana Conference 2022

Why are we here?

February 2022
**Outbreak
of the war**

June 2022
**Webinar: Cultural
heritage threats in
Ukraine and the role of
citizen engagement**

July 2022
**Challenge:
Ukrainian cultural
heritage threats, at
#EUSpace4Ukraine
hackathon**

Winter 2022
**Online resource on
open innovation in
academia-society
cooperation for
(Ukrainian) cultural
heritage**

September 30
Europeana Conference

Forms of citizen engagement in Ukrainian cultural heritage preservation

- #1 Open innovation actions
- #2 Cultural heritage networks triggering citizen engagement
- #3 Museum-driven actions
- #4 Citizen-driven actions

#EUSpace4Ukraine HACKATHON

Your ideas have the power to support people fleeing the devastating war. The hackathon takes place from:

29.06. - 01.07.2022

NOW OPEN FOR REGISTRATION

#EUSpace4Ukraine hackathon

BackUp
Ukraine

#1: Open
Innovation
actions

#Winners

 Maciej Kutyla Tymoteusz Zapala	 Somo Ikwuoma & Oliver Holly Piotr Okrój & Dzmitry Khilmonchik	 Dawid Piudowski & Antoni Zajko Oskar Bukowski
2nd Damage Map	1st Search4Ukraine	3rd Disinfo Fighter

Hackathon4Ukraine

SUCHO

#2: Cultural heritage networks triggering citizen engagement

European Creatives Hub Network

Read initiatives and news about Ukraine

- Sneak peek: MAX program's mobility support for Ukrainian creatives
- Creatives Unite Platform - now #StandsWithUkraine
- LIGHTHOUSE SESSIONS - A series of talks on welcoming Ukrainian refugees
- OPEN DOORS - Workspaces in
- Spreading the word: how to

uk Solidarity with Ukraine... Resources & Information Tech Backend Copy doc

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#CultureForUkraine

Resources & Information

Culture Action Europe

#CultureForUkraine

NEMO, Museums support Ukraine

Network of European Museum Organisations

Newsletter Events Press

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Home -> Advocacy -> Our Advocacy Work -> Museums support Ukraine

Museums support Ukraine

Following the war in Ukraine and after receiving calls and messages from colleagues from across Europe asking how they can support their Ukrainian colleagues, NEMO started collecting and monitoring support activities and initiatives organised by museums for Ukrainian colleagues and citizens.

#3: Museums-driven citizen engagement actions

The HERI initiative, Ukraine

Музейна ініціатива з реагування на збереження культурної спадщини в умовах війни та її пост-кризового відновлення
Museum task force aimed at responding to cultural heritage in times of warfare and its post-conflict recovery

#MOMuseum, Lithuania

#4: Citizen-driven actions in cultural heritage

#Lviv Open Lab

UNESCO crowd translation in Ukrainian language

Next steps...

Ready: A collection of open innovation initiatives on github

<https://web2learn.github.io/open-innovation-in-cultural-heritage/main.html>

EXAMPLES OF OPEN INNOVATION IN THE CULTURAL HERITAGE IN TIMES OF CRISIS

Driven by our strong belief that cultural heritage protection and preservation should be at the forefront of collective efforts, especially during conflicts, in this case the Ukrainian war, we felt the need to act by identifying initiatives highlighting the way open innovation can maximise the impact and effectiveness of such efforts to communities involved.

Stefania Oikonomou, Katerina Zourou

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Online open access learning resource

Expected: Winter 2022

- Unit 1: Open Innovation as crisis response in academia-society cooperation
- Unit 2: Open Innovation as response to cultural heritage crises
- Unit 3: Case study: Impact on Ukrainian cultural heritage
- Unit 4: Open Innovation in academia-society cooperation
- Unit 5: A concrete example of an open innovation initiative for cultural heritage in times of crisis

<https://echoing.eu/>

On 24 February, the news of the Russian invasion of Ukraine raised strong reactions from all over the world.

Among them, the cultural heritage community strongly condemned this attack and expressed its concern for the threats to Ukrainian cultural assets. Cultural heritage is the patrimony of a community, it preserves and perpetuates its memory, values and identity. **Destroying artworks, monuments, historic buildings and remnants of the past cancels with them the history and identity of the Ukrainians, adding an irreparable damage to the unacceptable losses of human lives and the distress of the population which is causing millions of refugees.**

SUM – Save the Ukraine Monument Interview with 4CH. English version

Resources

- eCHOIng project: <https://echoing.eu/>
- Copernicus Cultural Heritage Task Force. Report on the user requirements in the Copernicus domain to support Cultural Heritage management. conservation and protection. <https://ra.braze.unit.no/ra-xmlui/bitstream/handle/11250/2650038/Copernicus%20Cultural%20Heritage%20Task%20Force%20Report.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>
- (teaser video) Open innovation in academia-society cooperation: examples from cultural heritage field <https://vimeo.com/709996557>
- INOS project. (June 10, 2022), Cultural heritage threats and the role of citizen engagement inside and outside academia”, <https://inos-project.eu/2022/06/14/report-cultural-heritage-threats-and-the-role-of-citizen-engagement-inside-and-outside-universities/>
- Jansen-Dings, I., van Dijk, D., van Westen, R. (2017), Hacking culture: A how to guide for hackathons in the cultural sector, Waag society, <https://waag.org/sites/waag/files/media/publicaties/es-hacking-culture-spreads.pdf>

Thank you

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